

YOUTH SLANG OF MODERN TEENAGER

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ABSTRACT

The article describes the modern speech culture. The reasons for using slang words by young people are explained. Most of the time a teenager tries to stand out by using youth slang, read the boxes, the developments to which they belong. Belonging to a certain subculture, breaking existing rules, management of emotional stress. Given the results of experimental research that allow the creation of the formula. Ideas about characteristics of teenagers slang in everyday life.

Key words: teenager, youth slang, speech culture, speech culture of teenager.

The problem of the speech culture of the younger generation worries many today scientists. Speech is a specific form of reflection of reality.

The teenage period of development is determined by the intermediate provisions. On the one hand, a teenager is no longer a child. On the other hand, he has not yet become an adult. This uncertainty causes internal contradictions and conflicts that are expressed in protest forms of behavior. Language is one of the forms of self-expression. Degree jargon in adolescent speech, according to research, exceeds 60%

for boys and 25% for girls [1].

Several have been identified in the literature reasons for the use of youth slang and jargon by teenagers. Among them:

- deliberate shocking, which manifests itself in the desire to stand out, challenge others, break existing rules;
- an uncontrollable outburst of emotions, expressed in strong expressing an emotional reaction to an event;
- manifestation of belonging to a certain subculture, demonstration of adherence to fashion for the use of certain words;
- poor vocabulary, inability to navigate the situation highest emotional upsurge [2].

To study the features of the use of youth slang in oral speech of adolescents, we conducted a pilot study, in which involved students from grades 9 to 11 School number 290. The total number of students participating in the study was 90 people.

They had to rank youth slang words by frequency use in speech. The proposed list contained the words of the following parts speeches: nouns (for example: homework, zhmot, etc.), verbs (for example: run over, throw, flatten, etc.), adverbs (dumbly, in any way, etc.), adjectives (cool, sensible, clueless, etc.), interjections (well, damn it, etc.).

As a result of data analysis, results were obtained. First the group, which included words most often used in speech, consisted of nouns. These are words that name parts of the body (turnip - head, scoreboard - face). And also words aimed at insulting (brake - slow reaction, yap - a person who does not know how to keep his word). To the second group verbs included. Their semantics mainly reflects feelings or actions (flashes - I feel bad, throw - to deceive). The third group activity of use in speech consisted of adverbs (dumb - bad, healthy - Fine). In fourth place were adjectives.

Analysis of word formations carried out by O.M. Krainik showed that in there are two trends in the slang of modern schoolchildren. With one On the other hand, slang is replenished due to the active borrowing of words from other languages. On the other hand, to many foreign words in slang neoplasms are added [3].

The syntactic structure of a teenager's speech, according to research by V.A. Kozyreva, N.A. Ludilshchikova, S.V. Moshchevoy, presented mainly simple two-part sentences, in rare cases common. From the point of view of the lexical content of the word, used by a teenager are limited to a certain area of activity, communicating with friends, spending free time [4; 5; 6].

Analysis of the presented studies allows us to formulate several provisions and conclusions that are relevant for modern education. Firstly, a teenager's desire to stand out is age-related feature of personal maturation. This should not place the student in position of confrontation with an adult. It is important that with the development and with the development of man, youth jargon has ceased to be relevant. On it was replaced by other values, and a language reflecting a view of the world certain age period gradually acquired features literary norm. Secondly, when teaching a language, it is often not taken into account conditions for real communication between students. In Focus the teacher is most often located in the language itself, the language system, and not the personality, reproducing this language in a certain speech situation. This creates reluctance among students to use the results in practice teachings.

In light of the above, it seems appropriate to study and description of a teenager's speech. This makes it possible to understand the level of proficiency

norms of literary language and determines modern trends language development in general.

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